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Recycling of the end-of-life lightweight aggregate concrete (LWAC) with a novel approach

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Abstract

This work proposed an environmental-friendly approach for high-grade recycling of the end-of-life LWAC. The mechanical performance of mortar with recycled powder (RP), mortar with recycled fine aggregate (RFA) and recycled lightweight aggregate concrete (RLWAC) were investigated. Microstructure of mortar and RLWAC was detected to identify the properties of interfacial transition zone (ITZ). RP can prolong the setting of reference cement and the 10 % dosage is better than 2 % in not only retarding effect but also strength development. An appropriate content of RFA is beneficial for compressive strength. Replacing standard sand with 10 % RFA increases the compressive strength of mortar by approximately 10 %. However, a high replacement content (40 %) of RFA brings about a reduction of compressive strength. The amount of RFA below 20% will not increase the dry shrinkage of mortar. The compressive strength of RLWAC is reduced by 10 % RLWA but it has a significant increase when the replacement content reaches 30 %. In mortar with RFA, cracks initiate from the ITZ of new sand and new paste and few cracks generate from old paste and old sand. Four types of ITZ that have distinct features are observed between cement paste and LWA in RLWAC.

Keywords: Sustainable concrete; Recycled powder; Recycled fine aggregate; Recycled lightweight aggregate; Interfacial transition zone;

Abbreviations

LWAC, Lightweight aggregate concrete;

LWA, Lightweight aggregate

RP, Recycled powder

ITZ, Interfacial transition zone

RFA, Recycled fine aggregate

RLWAC, Recycled lightweight aggregate concrete

C&D, Construction and demolition

RA, Recycled coarse aggregate

- 1 NWC, Normal weight aggregate concrete
- 2 R-42.5, Reference cement
- 3 PO. 52.5R, Ordinary Portland cement
- 4 BSEM, backscatter scanning electron microscope
- 5 XRD, X-ray diffraction
- 6 PSD, Particle size distribution
- 7 C-S-H, Calcium silicate hydrate

8 **1. Introduction**

9 As the rapid development and universal urbanization, an extensive demand of cement
10 and concrete in civil engineering continues to climb around the world. Latest data
11 imply that the annual demand of concrete was about 33 billion tons (Mehta and
12 Monteiro, 2019). Manufacturing such an amount of concrete depleted considerable
13 nonrenewable natural resources such as soil, limestone and river sand. Moreover, the
14 greenhouse and acid gas emissions during production of cement also posed many
15 environmental problems. In the meantime, the reconstruction of old buildings and
16 bridges led to plenty of construction and demolition (C&D) waste. Almost a half of
17 municipal solid derived from C&D waste in China (Ding and Xiao, 2014). The solid
18 waste not only occupies considerable land but also frequently pollutes soils, water and
19 air (Wu et al., 2018). Therefore, for the purpose of sustainable development, many
20 investigations were carried out to convert the C&D waste into resource that can be
21 reused as resources, such as recycled coarse aggregate (RA) (Verian et al., 2018).

22
23 It is not hard to find two categories of concrete in C&D wastes, normal weight
24 aggregate concrete (NWC) and also LWAC. The typical recycling procedure for NWC
25 is particle homogenization, grinding and sieving, and autogenous cleaning (Pepe et al.,
26 2014). This procedure can easily collect RA, but to obtain RFA with good quality
27 requires more effort (Guo et al., 2018). Therefore, converting NWC into RA has been
28 fully investigated from the recycling process, mechanical performance and durability
29 aspect. Some focus on influence of RA on the mechanical performance of recycled
30 aggregated concrete (Xu et al., 2018; Silva et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2019). The other
31 have paid attention on the durability of RCA (Xuan et al., 2017; Dimitriou et al., 2018;
32 Zhu et al., 2019). A few literatures reported the utilization of recycling fine aggregate
33 (RFA) from C&D waste, and the RFA can even be used to produce ultrahigh
34 performance concrete. (Stefanidou et al., 2014; Bourguiba et al., 2017; Jiang et al.,
35 2019). Moreover, the crushing process of C&D waste would bring about waste
36 powder. If it was pulverized into specific fineness, the recycled powder (RP) can
37 partially replace Portland cement in concrete as supplementary cementitious materials
38 (Xiao et al., 2018), However, it is not easy to collect RFA and RP that is beneficial for

1 concrete by traditional recycling process.

2

3 LWAC is more suitable for some civil engineering construction than NWC, since it
4 has better properties than NWC in some constructions like long span bridges, floating
5 and offshore platforms due to its low density ($500\text{-}2000\text{ kg/cm}^3$), and high
6 strength/density ratio (Giro-Paloma et al., 2019; Zhou and Brooks, 2019). An
7 emblematic example is the construction of Nanjing Yangtze River bridge in China in
8 1968. The upper deck of this bridge was established with 5615 m^3 LWAC. Compared
9 with ordinary concrete, the weight of deck was reduced by 0.5 t/m^3 . That cut the
10 steels requirement for constructing the railway deck (Huang et al., 2019). Besides
11 China, the utilization of LWAC in long span bridges can be found in many other
12 countries, such as Raftsund bridge in Norway, and Auckland bay steel truss
13 suspension bridge in America.

14

15 The main difference between LWAC and NWC is coarse aggregate mixed in concrete.
16 The coarse aggregate of LWAC, lightweight aggregate (LWA), is usually made by
17 sintering of expanded clay (Muñoz-Ruiperez et al., 2016), expanded shale (Cui et al.,
18 2012) and some solid waste (Ayati et al., 2019). Production of LWA normally needs a
19 sintering temperature up to $1300\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Although the addition of flux may reduce the
20 temperature to $1000\text{-}1100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (Wei et al., 2018), the production of LWA still has a high
21 consumption of energy and depletion of nonrenewable natural resources like
22 expanded clay and expanded shale. Furthermore, recovery and reconstruction of old
23 constructions made by LWAC would render landfill issues as NWC. Hence, the best
24 way for dealing with end-of-life LWAC is recycling in high-grade. That can not only
25 get rid of environmental problems from landfilling but also lower the environmental
26 impact from production of LWAC.

27

28 However, few literatures reported an appropriate method for dealing with the
29 end-of-life LWAC in high-grade. Recycling method for NWC which normally
30 consists of two crushing steps and several sifting steps (Xiao et al., 2018) is not
31 practicable for LWAC. Because the LWA is weaker than the hardened cement paste,
32 dealing with the end-of-life LWAC with this method will fractured old LWA into
33 pieces so that the recycled aggregate may have a higher density but lower strength
34 than original LWA. This kind of low-grade RCA can only be treated in low
35 value-added route such as for road base materials, and options for low-graded reuse
36 will become more limited (Zhang et al., 2019). Hence, herein we explore the higher
37 value-added solutions for the end-of-life LWAC than traditional approach. The
38 high-grade RLWA would be used to produce sustainable concrete with good

1 performance.

2

3 This work presented a novel approach for high-grade reuse of a 50-year end-of-life
4 LWAC. This approach can separate most of the LWA from the LWAC avoiding
5 fracture. In addition, we can collect RFA and RP in this process to reuse as renewable
6 resources. The influence of RP on the setting time, hydration progress and mechanical
7 performance of Portland cement was detected. The appropriate experiments were
8 carried out to reveal how RFA affects the mechanical performance, dry shrinkage and
9 microstructure of cement mortar. RLWA were used to replace the new LWA to
10 produce RLWAC, in order that we could assess the feasibility of reusing RLWA from
11 this novel approach. The compressive strength of RLWAC and microstructure of ITZ
12 were analyzed to demonstrate the effect of RLWA on performance of RLWAC.
13 Particularly, we identified the ITZ in cement past with RFA and four types of ITZ in
14 RLWAC which is meaningful for understanding the influence of microstructure on the
15 mechanical performance and durability of RLWAC.

16

17 **2. Materials and methods**

18 2.1 Novel recycling procedure

19 The novel recycling procedure is inspired by the freezing and thawing damage of
20 concrete. While the porous concrete absorbed water, then underwent freezing and
21 thawing, it would suffer the hydraulic pressure, ice crystallization pressure and the
22 force from mismatch of thermal effects between ice and solid phases (Ausloos et al.,
23 1999; Liu et al., 2014, 2018; Smith et al., 2019). Those coupling effects lead concrete
24 to generate crack at a certain freezing and thawing circulation. Suffering enough
25 circulation will separate concrete into pieces without breaking aggregates. Therefore,
26 we invented a recycling procedure based on the freezing and thawing. Comparing
27 with the traditionally recycling procedure, this process has two main benefits:

28

29 High-grade recycle: grinding steps in normal process is bond to fracture LWA into
30 pieces so that the recycled aggregate may have higher density but lower strength than
31 original LWA. A few researchers recycled the lightweight expanded clay aggregate
32 concrete by crushing (Bogas et al., 2015). It can only collect RLWA stuck with paste
33 whose density and water absorption ability was much higher than original LWA. This
34 low-grade RLWA could only use to produce RLWAC with much higher density but
35 lower strength. The novel procedure in this paper can avoid the fracture and collect
36 the RP, RFA and RLWA with good quality.

37

1 Environmental friendly: this novel process can avoid grinding. Therefore, it will not
 2 generate the dusts and noise from grinding process. Moreover, the freezing and
 3 thawing circulation can implement through nature temperature change. It is easy to
 4 carry out in some areas that have large difference in temperature between day and
 5 night. This can save much more energy.

6

7 As shown in Fig. 1, the 50-year end-of-life LWAC was firstly cut into proper
 8 dimension whose side is under 1 m for handling convenience. The blocks were then
 9 dipped into water for approximate 24 h. After that, the blocks were transferred into a
 10 machine in which the specimens go through a freezing-thawing cycle between -1 °C
 11 and 1 °C. Afterwards, the RLWA, RFA and RP could be completely separated after
 12 50-100 cycles. Finally, the water would be filtered and reused for dipping. The solid
 13 phase dried under air condition then it was sifted to obtain RP, RFA and RLWA.
 14 Comparing with the traditionally recycling procedure for NWC, this approach reduces
 15 the noise and dust pollution from cracking and grinding. The significant point is that
 16 the RLWA can avoid being crushed into pieces. Fig. 2 presents the image of RP, RFA
 17 and RLWA. The sphere RLWA was covered with a few of old pastes and some old
 18 pastes particles mixed in the RFA.

19

20 Fig. 1 The procedure of novel recycling approach, including appropriate dicing, dipping, water soaking,
 21 loop of freezing and thawing, filtering, drying and sifting.

1
2 Fig. 2 The image of recycled ingredients. After drying and sieving the RP, RFA and RLWA with good
3 quality can be collected.

4 2.2 Materials and experiments

5 The 50-year LWAC was collected from the recovery of Nanjing Yangtze River bridge
6 (Huang et al., 2019). Reference cement (R-42.5) without addition of supplementary
7 cementitious materials was supplied by Lucheng cement co. LTD. (Shandong,China).
8 Ordinary Portland cement (PO. 52.5R) was purchased from Onoda cement co. LTD.
9 (Shanghai, China). Table 1 shows the chemical composition of those two types of
10 cement. The ISO standard sand was purchased form Xiamen eso standard sand co.
11 LTD. (Xiamen, China). The river sand was supplied by shengkuo building materials
12 co., LTD (Shanghai, China). The fly ash LWA obtained from Shandong Chambroad
13 HoldingGroup Co., Ltd. was chosen as reference. The proportions for testing the
14 influence of RP and RFA on the performance and microstructures of cement mortar
15 are presented in table 2 and 3 respectively. Table 4 shows the mix proportion for
16 RLWAC. Note that the weight of LWA and RLWA is the wet weight after pre-wetted
17 for 24 h.

18 2.3 Experiments

19 The setting time of cement paste was determined according to ISO 9597:2008 by
20 means of Vicat apparatus. After normative mixing, cement mortar was casted in a
21 mould (40 mm × 40 mm × 160 mm), and demoulded after 24 h air curing. The flexural
22 and compressive strength of mortars were measured at 3, 7 and 28 days according to
23 ISO 679: 1989. RLWAC was casted in a cubic mould with a side of a 100 mm and it
24 was also demoulded after 24 h air curing. The compressive strength was tested after
25 curing 7 and 28 days referring to Chinese standard GB 50107-2010. The fragments of
26 mortar and RLWAC from strength test at 28d were immersing in the ethanol for
27 stopping hydration through solvent exchange. Then it was dried in air and prepared

1 for backscatter scanning electron microscope (BSEM) test.

2
3 Particle size distribution of sand was tested according to Chinese stand GB/T
4 14684-2011. Drying shrinkage test of cement mortar was operated referring to
5 Chinese standard JGJ/T70-2009, prisms of 40 mm × 40 mm × 160 mm were prepared
6 for experiments. The drying shrinkage value of specimens at every curing age was
7 calculated by the equation:

$$\varepsilon_t = \frac{L_0 - L_t}{L - L_b}$$

8
9 where: ε_t —drying shrinkage value of specimens at relevant curing time; L_0 —the initial
10 length of specimens embedded with metal head, mm; L_t —the length of specimen
11 measured at t days, mm; L —the length of specimen, 160 mm; L_b —the length of two
12 shrinkage head embedded in the mortar, 20 ± 2 mm.

13
14 Table 1 Chemical composition analysis of reference cement and Portland cement.

Sample	Chemical composition /%							
	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	CaO	MgO	SO ₃	Na ₂ O _{eq}	f-CaO
R-42.5	22.49	4.57	3.38	63.10	2.41	2.35	0.509	0.76
PO 52.5R	20.9	4.56	3.23	65.00	0.65	2.65		

15
16 Table 2 Mix proportion for strength test of cement mortar with RP.

Samples	Weight /g			
	Water	Sand	R-42.5 cement	RP
Control	225	1350	450	0
1% RP	225	1350	450	4.5
2% RP	225	1350	450	9

17
18 Table 3 Mix proportion for strength test of cement mortar with RFA.

Samples	Weight /g			
	Water	Standard sand	RFA	PO.52.5 Cement
Control	225	1350	0	450
10% RFA	225	1215	135	450
20% RFA	225	1080	270	450
40% RFA	225	810	540	450

19
20 Table 4 Mix proportion for one cubic meter RLWAC.

Samples	Weight /kg				
	Water	PO.52.5 cement	River sand	Reference LWA	RLWA
Control	144	403	633	830	0
10% RLWA	144	403	633	747	83
20% RLWA	144	403	633	664	166
30% RLWA	144	403	633	581	249

21 2.4 Test methods

22 The particle size distribution (PSD) of RP was determined by a laser particle size
23 tester (LS230 0.04um-2000um, Becrman Coulter Ltd., American). A Rigaku

1 International Corporation D/max 2550 VB3+/PC diffractometer (Cu K α radiation)
2 was used to test X-ray diffraction (XRD) of RP. It was operated at the range of 5-60°
3 (2 θ) with a scan speed of 2°/min, a tube voltage of 40 kV and a current of 250 mA.

4
5 Hydration heat flow of cement was measured at 20 °C with a water/cement ratio of
6 0.5 by TAM Air Isothermal Calorimeter from TA Instruments (TAM air C80,
7 Thermometric, Sweden). Samples and water were tempered at 20 °C for 30 minutes
8 before mixing. The binder put into the ampere bottle, then water was injected into it
9 and the slurry was homogeneously stirred with a glass rod for about 30 sec. The data
10 logging started from water addition time to 24 h.

11
12 The crushed fragments were oven-dried and vacuum impregnated with lucid and low
13 viscosity epoxy resin. After the resin hardened, all specimens were polished with a
14 decrease grade of SiC papers from 800 to 2000 mesh, before being polished with
15 diamond crystallites from 3 μ m to 0.25 μ m. Backscatter scanning electron microscopy
16 (BSEM) image analysis was performed to determine the cracks and the microstructure
17 of ITZ. The polished sections plated with gold were examined by a Nova NanoSEM
18 450 (14001-2004, America) at an accelerating voltage of 15-30 kV and a spot size of
19 4.0, coupled with an energy dispersive X-ray spectrometer to gather elements map
20 information.

22 **3. Results and discussion**

23 3.1 Properties of RP, RFA and RLWA

24 Fig. 3 presents the PSD of RP. There are about a half of the RP whose particle size are
25 below 10 μ m. The majority of particles are with the size between 1 μ m and 50 μ m.
26 The mineral composition determined by XRD (Fig. 4) shows that main crystal
27 ingredient is CaCO₃ which is the products from carbonation of portlandite and
28 calcium silicate hydrate (C-S-H) (Monkman et al., 2016; Zhu et al., 2018; Qin and
29 Gao, 2019). This process can uptake CO₂ in air to cut down the environmental impact
30 from concrete (Di Filippo et al., 2019). The other ingredients of RP comprise of
31 C-S-H (gismondine, tacharanite and hillebrandite) which is the main hydration
32 production of silicates in cement, the silica that is the composition from river sand and
33 ettringite that is the hydration products of reaction between tricalcium aluminate and
34 gypsum.

35
36 Table 5 illustrates some physical properties of RFA, river sand and standard sand. The
37 bulk and dry density of RFA is lowest among the three kinds of sand. It demonstrates

1 the highest porosity of RFA because of some hardened pastes mixed in RFA. River
 2 sand and standard sand has the similar bulk and dry density but evident different
 3 fineness modulus. Fineness modulus is a parameter applied to index the fineness of
 4 sand referred to GB/T 14684-2011, and the lower value relates to the finer sand. PSD
 5 in Fig. 5 reveals that river sand is the finest, corresponding to the lowest fineness
 6 modulus. RFA has highest fineness modulus but its pass percentage has continuous
 7 distribution.

8

9 Table 6 concludes the properties of RLWA, original LWA used in 50-year LWAC and
 10 reference LWA. The bulk and dry density of LWA increases after recycling, but the
 11 density of RLWA is similar to reference LWA. Interestingly, RLWA has the lowest
 12 one-hour water absorption. For better understanding, the BESM images were detected
 13 and presented in Fig. 6. We can observe in Fig. 2 that partial surface of RLWA is
 14 smooth without adhered old paste. This part corresponds to B region in Fig. 6 (a).
 15 However, the majority of the surface is covered with pastes like A region. Those
 16 adhered pastes connected with the paste filled in the open pores of in LWA (Huang et
 17 al., 2019). Ca and Al element map in Fig. 6 (b) clearly demonstrates the paste filled in
 18 open pores of old LWA. Therefore, we suppose that the lowest one-hour water
 19 absorption of RLWA is because of the adhered paste filling open pores.

20

21

Fig. 3 Particle size distribution of RP.

Fig. 4 X-ray diffraction pattern of RP.

Table 5 Physical properties of sand.

Samples	Bulk density (g/cm ³)	Dry density (g/cm ³)	Fineness modulus
RFA	1.32	2.38	3.69
Standard sand	1.73	2.51	2.87
River sand	1.62	2.49	2.35

Fig. 5 Particle size distribution of sands.

Table 6 Properties of RLWA, Original LWA and Reference LWA.

Physical properties	Bulk density (kg/m ³)	Dry particle density (kg/m ³)	One-hour water absorption
RLWA	926	1882	10.61%

Original LWA	676	1255	12.50%
Reference LWA	969	1914	14.30%

1

BSE image of RLWA surface

2

3

4

(a) BSEM image of RLWA surface, A: a layer of old paste adhering on the surface of RLWA, B: surface without old paste.

5

6

7

8

(b) Elements map of RLWA surface.

Fig. 6 Microscopic images of a RLWA surfaces with old pastes.

3.2 The retarding effect of RP

Several appropriate utilization situations of recycled ingredients were investigated. RP was tried to apply as a retarder for cement. Normally, gypsum was added into cement clinker as to control the setting of cements (Beaudoin and Odler, 2019) but in this paper we use RP as setting control agent. As shown in Fig. 7, RP has the retarding

1 effect on reference cement. The dosage of 1% RP can prolong the initial setting for 20
2 mins but 2% RP does not exert better effect on initial setting. The effect on final
3 setting time is more evident. It increased from 279 min to 312 min with the addition
4 of 1% RP. 2% RP has a weaker retarding effect than 1% RP.

5

6 The data in Fig. 7 reveal that the hydration rate has been reduced by RP before 24 h.
7 Although the duration of induction period of cement with RP is similar to control, the
8 hydration rate in induction period and acceleration period has been evidently
9 suppressed. The cumulative hydration heat of pure reference is much higher than
10 cement with RP. This is consistent with data in previous research (Wang et al., 2018).
11 The addition of residues like FGD gypsum into cement as retarders is tend to sacrifice
12 the early strength development (Caillahua and Moura, 2018). However, the
13 compressive strength of cement with 1% RP has an increase comparing to pure
14 reference cement paste with an increment of 3.81% after 7 days curing and 3.07 %
15 after 28 days curing, respectively. Compressive strength of cement mortar with 2%
16 RP is the highest at 7d, but it is lowest at 28d. Therefore, combining with the setting
17 time, the optimum addition of RP as retarder is 1%. It can not only control setting but
18 also is beneficial for compressive strength development.

19

20

21

22

Fig. 7 The setting time of cement pastes with RP.

1
2

Fig. 8 Hydration heat of cement with different content of RP.

3
4

Fig. 9 Compressive strength of cement paste with RP at 3d, 7d and 28d.

5 3.3 Utilization of RFA

6 A few of literatures reported the utilization of RFA, because the traditional recycling
 7 procedure is hard to separate sand from old concrete. A limited number of
 8 investigations reported the water absorption features of RFA and complicated
 9 treatment for using in ultra-high performance cement-based composites (Yacoub et al.,
 10 2018; Jiang et al., 2019). Fig. 1 demonstrates that the novel recycling procedure can
 11 collect RFA conveniently. To demonstrate the feasibility of reusing RFA from the

1 novel procedure, the influence of RFA on the mechanical performance of cement
2 mortar was investigated. Fig. 10 shows the flexural strength of control mortar and
3 mortar with 10%, 20% and 40% RFA. The flexural strength of mortar at 7d presents
4 not much difference with replacement of RFA. Indeed a 40% replacement has an
5 increase of flexural strength at 28d. Fig. 11 demonstrates that the compressive
6 strength of mortar develops quickly up to 30 MPa at 7d, because the cement used in
7 this mortar is PO. 52.5 R that is a kind of high-early-strength cement. A 10%
8 replacement of standard can improve the compressive strength by approximate 10%.
9 However, when the replacement content reaches 40% it brings about 10% reduction
10 of compressive strength. It should be noted that replacing with 20% RFA results in
11 few influences on the compressive strength of mortar at 28d.

12
13 Dry shrinkage is another main concern for the utilization of recycled aggregate. The
14 previous articles reported that a porous surface feature of recycled aggregate induced
15 a high water-absorption. That may result in a higher dry shrinkage and cracking
16 (Bendimerad et al., 2016; Gonzalez-Corominas and Etxeberria, 2016). However, if the
17 recycled aggregates were pre-saturated, it would show a good potential of self-healing
18 at long term (Bendimerad et al., 2016). In this work, the dry shrinkage of cement
19 mortar with RFA without pre-wetting was tested (Fig. 12). Before 28d, a 10% RFA
20 replacement keeps the dry shrinkage of mortar stay at the lowest level, since that
21 amount of RFA will absorb a certain content of water which will not lead too much
22 dry shrinkage. Instead the absorbed water can exert a internal curing effect (Lee et al.,
23 2018). The dry shrinkage of mortar with 20% RFA replacement is similar to control
24 mortar before 21d, and it is larger at 28d. The 40 % RFA replacement causes an
25 evident increase of dry shrinkage.

26
27 In order to uncover the influence of RFA on the microstructure of mortar, the typical
28 BSEM image of mortar was collected. Fig. 13 shows a region where a new river sand
29 connected with new paste, RFA connecting with new paste and old paste connecting
30 with new paste can be observed. Combining the image in (a) with elements map in (b),
31 new paste, old paste and RFA can be clearly distinguished. We can observe that many
32 cracks were initiated from the ITZ of new sand and new paste. A few of cracks were
33 generated from old paste and old sand. It can be explained by the elastic modulus
34 differences between sand and new pastes. Old pastes and new pastes have similar
35 elastic modulus but the modulus of new sand and pastes is seriously inconsistent. In
36 addition, wider ITZ is observed in elements map between new sand and paste
37 compared with old pastes and sand. However, more pores are induced in the zone
38 between new and old paste because of the water absorption of old pastes. That

1 explains why the 40 % RFA replacement will lead to a lower compressive strength but
2 replacement content below 20 % may not.

3

4

5

Fig. 10 Flexural strength of cement mortar with different replacement of RFA.

6

7

8

Fig. 11 Compressive strength of cement mortar with different replacement of RFA.

Fig. 12 Dry shrinkage of cement mortar with different replacement of RFA.

(a) BSEM image of mortar replaced with 40 % RFA, which contains new river sand, old sand, new pasta and old pasta.

1

2 (b) Related elements map of BSEM images of mortar replaced with 40 % RFA, where the new river
 3 sand, old sand, new paste and old paste can be easily identified.

4 Fig. 13 BSEM image and its elements map of mortar replaced with 40 % RFA at 28d.

5 3.4 Utilization of RLWA

6 Many studies have been carried out to assess the performance of concrete adding with
 7 recycled aggregate from end-of-life normal weight concrete and more than one
 8 thousand literatures were published on journals (Chen et al., 2019; Jin et al., 2019).
 9 The main topics focused on influence of moisture and paste coverage condition on
 10 workability of fresh concrete mix and mechanical performance of hardened recycled
 11 concrete (Poon et al., 2004; Etxeberria et al., 2007). Others tried to use the porous
 12 structure of recycled aggregate to reserve moisture for internal curing (Wijayasundara
 13 et al., 2018; Liu et al., 2019). Most results showed that the utilization of RA led to a
 14 decrease in the flowability, compressive strength and modulus of elasticity of concrete
 15 (Medina et al., 2014; Velay-Lizancos et al., 2018). Those negative effects related to
 16 the wider and weaker ITZ of concrete with RA(Sáez del Bosque et al., 2017),
 17 However, The RLWA from this novel approach may show different influence on the
 18 performance of RLWAC, Therefore, the main purpose of this section is to evaluate
 19 mechanical performance and ITZ of RLWAC.

20

21 As shown in Fig. 14, replacing with 10 % and 20 % RLWA rarely influences the
 22 compressive strength of RLWAC at 7d. The replacement of 30 % RLWA increases
 23 compressive strength of concrete by about 14.2 %. Up to 28d, the compressive
 24 strength of LWAC does not show much increase from 7d. It is for the reason that the
 25 weakest phase in LWAC is the LWA. The long-term compressive strength of RLWAC

1 mainly depends on the strength of weakest phase (Sims et al., 2019) That is reference
 2 LWA, RLWAC and ITZ. The compressive strength of control LWAC is 35.12 MPa at
 3 28d, and 10 % RLWA replacement reduces it to 34.10 MPa. However, the
 4 compressive strength of RLWAC with 20 % replacement is similar to control, and
 5 30 % RLWA increases the strength up to 37.30 MPa.

6
 7 Fig. 14 Compressive strength of RLWAC with 0, 10 %, 20 % and 30 % RLWA replacement at 7d and
 8 28d.

9
 10 BSEM images of ITZ were collected for understanding the implication of RLWA on
 11 the microstructure and strength development of RLWAC. Four types of ITZ between
 12 cement paste and LWA have been identified in RLWAC. Fig. 15 presents the most
 13 typical ITZ category that is between the new paste and reference LWA. Reference
 14 LWA has a smooth and dense surface so that it creates the ITZ with a distinct porous
 15 feature and with a thickness of about 50-100 μm (Kong et al., 2015; Vargas et al.,
 16 2017; Huang et al., 2019). Fig. 16 displays the ITZ between the new paste and RLWA
 17 covered with old paste. The thickness of covered old paste is about 100 μm and we
 18 can observe the old ITZ between the old paste and RLWA. The new ITZ comprises of
 19 old ITZ and the old paste. It is much denser but thicker than the ITZ in Fig. 15. Ca
 20 element map in Fig. 16 (b) illustrates that the covered old paste has inserted into pores
 21 of old LWA but the structure of old ITZ is porous. Hence, this kind of ITZ may be
 22 weaker than ITZ in Fig. 15. The third kind of ITZ is presented in Fig 17 that is the
 23 ITZ between new paste and RLWA filled with old paste. The thickness of this ITZ is
 24 about 40-50 μm which is much smaller than ITZ between reference LWA and paste. It

1 is denser than ITZ in Fig. 16 and few cracks cross this zone.

2

3 Fig. 18 presents the ITZ between new paste and RLWA without old paste. The rough
4 and porous surficial nature of RLWA in Fig. 18 (a) results from the exfoliation of
5 surface shell during recycling. That facilitates the paste penetrate into the inner part of
6 RLWA to form an inlaid zone instead of ITZ. This zone is much denser than ITZ, and
7 the elements map implies that its periphery is even denser than the ITZ of sands. To
8 conclude, the weakest ITZ is between the new paste and RLWA covered with old
9 paste. The strongest ITZ is between new paste and RLWA without old paste. Most
10 ITZ of RLWA is stronger than that of reference LWA, unless the RLWA is covered
11 with too much old paste.

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13

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Fig. 15 BESM image of ITZ between reference LWA and new paste.

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(a) BSEM image of ITZ between new paste and RLWA covered with old paste from RLWAC with 30% RLWA replacement at 28d.

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(b) Elements map of ITZ between new paste and RLWA covered with old paste

Fig. 16 BESM image and elements map of ITZ between new paste and RLWA covered with old paste from RLWAC with 30% RLWA replacement at 28d.

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7
8

(a) BSEM image of ITZ between new paste and RLWA filled with a few old paste.

9
10

(b) Elements map of ITZ between new paste and RLWA filled with a few old paste.

1 Fig. 17 BESM image and elements map of ITZ between new paste and RLWA filled with old paste
 2 from RLWAC with 30% RLWA replacement at 28d.

3
 4 (a) BSEM image of ITZ between new paste and RLWA filled without old paste.

5

6
 7 (b) Elements map of ITZ between new paste and RLWA without old paste

8 Fig. 18 BESM image and elements map of ITZ between new paste and RLWA without old paste
 9 from RLWAC with 30% RLWA replacement at 28d.

10 **4. Conclusions**

11 An environmentally friendly approach was proposed in this work. It is able to collect
 12 RP, RFA and RLWA with high quality from the end-of-life LWAC. To explore the
 13 feasibility of using recycled ingredients from this approach, we investigated the
 14 setting time cement with RP, compressive strength and shrinkage of mortar with RFA
 15 and mechanical performance of RLWAC with RLWA. Microstructure of mortar and
 16 RLWAC was detected to reveal the properties of ITZ in mortar and RLWAC. The
 17 main results are as follow:

18

1 RP consists of CaCO_3 from the carbonation of hydration products, some silica from
2 sand, a few ettringite and C-S-H (gismondine, tacharanite and hillebrandite). An
3 appropriate amount (1%) of RP can retard the setting of reference cement, Meanwhile,
4 it increases the compressive strength of mortar with 3.07 %.

5
6 The bulk and dry density of RFA are lower than both standard sand and river sand.
7 The RFA has the highest fineness modulus but it has more continuous PSD than the
8 other. The replacement of RFA below 10 % improves the compressive strength of
9 mortar. However, 40 % RFA replacement brings about 10% reduction of compressive
10 strength. Mortar with 10 % RFA replacement has the lowest dry shrinkage. The
11 Higher replacement (40 %) leads to a severe increase of dry shrinkage. After loading,
12 many cracks initiate from the ITZ between new sand and new paste, and cracks
13 generated from old paste and old sand is fewer than that zone.

14
15 RLWA from this novel approach has a similar dry density to reference LWA. It has the
16 lower one-hour water absorption because the majority of surface is covered with old
17 pastes. The low replacement (10 % and 20 %) enforces none significant influence on
18 compressive strength of RLWAC at 7d. Interestingly, 30 % RLWA replacement has a
19 significant increment of compressive strength (with 14.2 %). Four types of ITZ are
20 observed between cement paste and LWA in RLWAC. The weakest ITZ is the between
21 the new paste and RLWA covered with old paste and the strongest ITZ is between
22 new paste and RLWA without old paste.

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29

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